

Gender and Justice: Rethinking the Protection of Women in Nigeria's Humanitarian Crises

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Abstract

Armed conflict and humanitarian crises in Nigeria continue to expose the gendered dimensions of suffering and vulnerability faced by victims, yet the legal frameworks designed to protect affected populations have failed to address the specific realities of women. While International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and International Human Rights Law (IHRL) contain strong provisions for the protection of civilians, the experiences of women in contexts such as Nigeria's prolonged insurgency reveal persistent gaps between these laws and the lived reality. This paper interrogates how international legal protections, though well-articulated in conventions and treaties, are undermined by socio-political structures, cultural norms, and institutional failures in Nigeria. It draws on the intersections of gender, conflict, and justice. Through a critical analysis of legal texts, humanitarian policies, and Nigeria's domestic implementation of IHL obligations, this paper rethinks the notion of "protection" in humanitarian law. It argues for a gender-responsive approach that transcends token inclusion and recognises women as agents of justice, peacebuilding, and legal reform. This paper ultimately proposes that the effectiveness of IHL depends not only on compliance by states and non-state actors but also on the transformation of the legal imagination itself, one that situates gender justice as central to humanitarian governance rather than peripheral to it.

1. Introduction

Armed conflict has never been gender-neutral. From ancient wars to contemporary insurgencies, the burdens of displacement, sexual violence, and social disintegration have fallen disproportionately upon women and girls.¹ Nigeria is the most populous country in the continent of Africa, however, the drawn out conflict in the North-East and other parts of the country, aggravated by the Boko Haram insurgency and other unnamed terrorists, and the resulting humanitarian crises, has laid bare the structural weaknesses of both international and domestic protection regimes. The very instruments of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) designed to safeguard civilians in armed conflict often falter when confronted with the intersection of gender, culture, and institutional failure.

¹ See, e.g., Judith Gardam and Michelle Jarvis, Women, Armed Conflict and International Law (Kluwer Law International 2001) 3–5.

The Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols, alongside key human rights instruments such as the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), establish clear obligations for state and non-state actors regarding the protection of women in conflict.² Yet, in many parts of Nigeria, these legal commitments remain aspirational. Women in internally displaced persons (IDP) camps, for instance, face prevalent sexual violence, economic marginalisation, and lack of access to justice, conditions that expose the discordance between international legal ideals and national realities.³

The humanitarian situation in Nigeria therefore offers a critical lens through which to interrogate the adequacy of existing legal frameworks. The challenge is not only one of implementation but of imagination: how law views “protection,” and whose voices shape its interpretation. Historically, women have been cast primarily as victims of war, bodies to be shielded rather than agents capable of redefining the contours of justice. This gendered construction of protection obscures the lived experiences of women who resist, rebuild, and reimagine life amid conflict.

This paper shall explore how International Humanitarian Law can move beyond a mere minimalist understanding of protection towards a more transformative model that places gender justice at its core. A Feminist legal methodology shall also be adopted to critique existing humanitarian norms and to identify pathways for a more inclusive and responsive framework of legal accountability in Nigeria’s humanitarian landscape.

This paper therefore pursues three interrelated questions:

1. To what extent do the principles of IHL and related human rights instruments adequately protect women in Nigeria’s humanitarian crises?

2. What legal, cultural, and institutional barriers hinder the enforcement of these protections?

² Geneva Convention Relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War (adopted 12 August 1949, entered into force 21 October 1950) 75 UNTS 287; Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (adopted 18 December 1979, entered into force 3 September 1981)

1249 UNTS 13.

³ Human Rights Watch, Nigeria: Officials Abusing Displaced Women, Girls (31 October 2016).

3. How might a gender-responsive reinterpretation of humanitarian law strengthen justice and accountability mechanisms for women in conflict-affected contexts?

By engaging these questions, this paper seeks to bridge the normative gaps between law and experience, thereby offering an interdisciplinary understanding of gender, justice, and humanitarian protection in today's Nigeria.

2. Conceptual and Legal Framework

2.1 Defining Gender, Protection, and Humanitarian Law

It is important to note that the protection of women in humanitarian crises must begin by cross-examining the concepts that uphold both the theory and practice of International Humanitarian Law (IHL).

“Gender” is a social and cultural concept. It is about social and cultural differences in identity, expression and experience as a man, woman or non-binary person.⁴ Within conflict and post-conflict contexts, gender functions as a determinant of vulnerability and agency, mediating how individuals experience displacement, violence, and justice.⁵ The recognition of gender as a structural variable has and continues to be central to the evolution of feminist legal theory, which challenges the seemingly neutral language of humanitarian norms.

The term “protection,” as used in IHL, covers a scope of obligations, which ranges from safeguarding civilians from direct hostilities to ensuring humane treatment, access to food, shelter, and medical care.⁶ However, protection is often interpreted in a paternalistic manner,

4 <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/standards/standard-sex-gender-variations-sex-characteristics-and-sexual-orientation-variables/latest-release#:~:text=Nominal%20definition,chromosomes%2C%20hormones%20and%20reproductive%20organs>

5 Dianne Otto, ‘Rethinking the Universality of Human Rights: Feminist and Queer Perspectives on International Law’ (2013) 1 *Journal of Human Rights Practice* 1.

6 ICRC, *What is International Humanitarian Law?* (ICRC 2004).

thereby positioning women as passive recipients of aid rather than active participants in their own security.⁷ Feminist scholars have therefore argued for a redefinition of protection that incorporates empowerment, participation, and accountability as essential components.⁸

International Humanitarian Law itself refers to the body of rules that regulate armed conflict, balancing military necessity with humanitarian considerations.⁹ Its core instruments, the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols, set out obligations towards non-combatants, including special protections for women and children.¹⁰ However, as the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) has observed, the “law in books” often fails to translate into “law in action,” particularly in fragile states where governance structures have eroded.¹¹

2.2 The International Legal Regime on Gender and Humanitarian Protection

The international legal regime for the protection of women in conflict is multidimensional and intersects International Humanitarian Law (IHL), International Human Rights Law (IHRL), and International Criminal Law (ICL). Central to this regime are the Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocol I (1977), which affirm the principle of humane treatment for all civilians and in a direct and frank manner recognises women’s particular needs during armed conflict.¹² Article 27 of the Fourth Geneva Convention provides that “women shall be especially protected against any attack on their honour, in particular against rape, enforced prostitution or any form of

⁷ Judith Gardam, *Women, Armed Conflict and International Law* (Kluwer Law International 2001) 55.

⁸ Christine Chinkin and Hilary Charlesworth, *The Boundaries of International Law: A Feminist Analysis* (Manchester University Press 2000).

⁹ ICRC (n 6) 3.

¹⁰ Geneva Conventions (n 2).

¹¹ ICRC, *International Humanitarian Law and Gender* (Background Paper, Geneva 2015).

¹² Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949 (Protocol I) (adopted 8 June 1977, entered into force 7 December 1978) 1125 UNTS 3.

indecent assault.”¹³

Complementary to IHL, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) emphasises the duty of states to eliminate gender-based discrimination “in all its forms,” including in times of crisis.¹⁴ The UN Security Council Resolution 1325 (2000) further advances the Women, Peace and Security (WPS) agenda by reinforcing women’s participation in peace processes and protection from conflict-related sexual violence.¹⁵ Together, these instruments indicate an international commitment to integrating gender perspectives into humanitarian governance.

In Africa, the Kampala Convention (2012), the African Union Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa, stands as a landmark regional treaty addressing internal displacement within a rights-based framework.¹⁶ It obliges member states, Nigeria included, to protect and assist displaced persons without discrimination, and to ensure the participation of women in decision-making processes.¹⁷ Also, The Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (the Maputo Protocol) similarly buttresses the right of women to dignity, freedom from violence, and participation in political and social life.¹⁸

2.3 The Domestic Legal Framework in Nigeria

Nigeria’s domestic legal order shows a very complex interplay between international obligations and national implementation. Although Nigeria has ratified most of the key instruments

¹³ Geneva Convention IV, Article 27.

¹⁴ CEDAW (n 2).

¹⁵ UNSC Res 1325 (31 October 2000) UN Doc S/RES/1325.

¹⁶ African Union Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa (adopted 23 October 2009, entered into force 6 December 2012).

¹⁷ *ibid*, arts 5–7.

¹⁸ Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (adopted 11 July 2003, entered into force 25 November 2005).

mentioned above, the translation of these norms into domestic law remains uneven. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) provides under Section 34 for the right to dignity of the human person and prohibits “torture, inhuman or degrading treatment.”¹⁹ However, the lack of a specific legislative framework designed to address gender-based violence in conflict zones or the entire country itself, limits the enforceability of such rights.

The Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015 (VAPP Act) represents a significant landmark in Nigeria’s gender justice landscape, criminalising various forms of violence, including rape and harmful traditional practices.²⁰ Yet, the Act’s limited territorial scope, applicable in the Federal Capital Territory and domesticated by all states except Kano State, creates disparities in protection, particularly in conflict-affected northern regions.²¹

Similarly, the National Policy on Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) and the National Action Plan on UNSCR 1325 provide policy frameworks for gender-sensitive humanitarian responses, but their implementation remains inconsistent.²² Sadly, weak institutional capacity, the lack of political will, and entrenched patriarchal norms continue to hinder progress.²³

The Nigerian context thus underlines the inconsistency of formal commitment without substantive compliance. While the legal architecture appears extensive or rather, comprehensive, the lived realities of women in conflict-affected areas reveal a deep systemic failure in accountability, access to justice, and protection delivery.

3. International Humanitarian Law and Gender

International Humanitarian Law (IHL) has evolved to protect those most vulnerable during armed conflict, however, its application to the specific experiences of women remains unequal. Although the four Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols of 1977 contain

¹⁹ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), s 34.

²⁰ Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015.

²¹ *ibid*

²² Federal Ministry of Women Affairs, National Action Plan for the Implementation of UNSCR 1325 and Related Resolutions (2017–2020).

²³ Amnesty International, Nigeria: “Our Job is to Shoot, Slaughter and Kill”: Boko Haram’s Reign of Terror in North-East Nigeria (2015).

provisions that recognize the special protection owed to women, this framework, though historically drafted through a gender-neutral lens, but in practice, privileges male combatants and ignores the distinct harms women face.²⁴ Over the past decades, feminist legal scholars and international tribunals have challenged this imbalance, arguing that genuine humanitarian protection must consider the intersection of gender, power, and armed violence.²⁵

3.1 Historical Foundations and Gender Blindness in IHL

The Geneva Conventions were designed to mitigate the suffering caused by war, grounded in principles of humanity, distinction, proportionality, and necessity. However, their interpretation and implementation have long reflected patriarchal assumptions.²⁶ For example, Article 27 of the Fourth Geneva Convention protects women against “ attacks on their honour, ” a conceptualization that primarily associates women’s dignity with sexual morality rather than with autonomy, equality, or physical integrity.²⁷ As Charlesworth and Chinkin note, this language reflects the “protectionist” rather than the “empowerment” approach hereby portraying women as passive victims rather than rights-bearing participants in armed conflict.²⁸

The Additional Protocols of 1977 introduced more specific prohibitions on gender-based violence, including rape, enforced prostitution, and indecent assault.²⁹ Nevertheless, these were framed

²⁴ Geneva Convention (IV) relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War (adopted 12 August 1949, entered into force 21 October 1950) 75 UNTS 287 (GC IV).

²⁵ H Charlesworth and C Chinkin, *The Boundaries of International Law: A Feminist Analysis* (Manchester University Press 2000) 230–235.

²⁶ F Ní Aoláin, ‘Gender and Armed Conflict: Challenges for International Humanitarian Law’ (2016) 92 *International Review of the Red Cross* 605.

²⁷ GC IV (n 1) art 27.

²⁸ Charlesworth and Chinkin (n 2) 238.

²⁹ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of Non-International Armed Conflicts

as crimes against “honour” or “family values,” rather than as violations of bodily integrity and human rights.³⁰ This failure to explicitly incorporate gender as a legal lens has meant that many atrocities against women, including sexual slavery, forced pregnancy, and gendered displacement, unfortunately were historically invisible in humanitarian discourse and accountability processes.

3.2 Feminist Critiques and the Evolution of Gender in IHL

The feminist engagement with IHL has redesigned the legal and moral understanding of how wars affect women. Scholars such as Christine Chinkin, Hilary Charlesworth, and Fionnuala Ní Aoláin have argued that traditional humanitarian law preserves gender hierarchies by prioritising combat-related harms (usually experienced by men) over social and reproductive harms (more commonly borne by women).³¹ This perspective gave rise to the concept of gender mainstreaming in international humanitarian and human rights law, which is a process whereby gender considerations must be integrated at all stages of policy and legal response to conflict.³²

This evolution became more pronounced after the conflicts in the former Yugoslavia and Rwanda, where systematic sexual violence was recognised as a tool of war and a crime under international law. The *Prosecutor v. Akayesu* judgment at the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) was a landmark moment, affirming that rape and sexual violence could constitute acts of genocide and crimes against humanity.³³ Similarly, the *Furundžija* case before the ICTY developed the legal definition of rape under customary international law and treated sexual

(Protocol II) (adopted 8 June 1977, entered into force 7 December 1978) 1125 UNTS 609 art 4(2)(e).

³⁰ J Gardam and M Jarvis, *Women, Armed Conflict and International Law* (Kluwer 2001) 47–52.

³¹ Charlesworth and Chinkin (n 2) 235–240.

³² UN Economic and Social Council, ‘Agreed Conclusions 1997/2: Mainstreaming the Gender Perspective into All Policies and Programmes in the United Nations System’ (1997).

³³ *Prosecutor v. Akayesu* (Judgment) ICTR-96-4-T (2 September 1998) paras 731–732.

violence as a grave breach of the Geneva Conventions.³⁴ These developments forced IHL to confront the gendered realities of armed conflict, not merely as collateral human suffering, but as deliberate strategies of domination and terror.

At the policy level, the adoption of UN Security Council Resolution 1325 (2000) on Women, Peace, and Security further established the responsibility of states and international institutions to protect women and ensure their participation in peace processes.³⁵ The Resolution marked a paradigm shift from viewing women solely as victims to recognising them as agents of peace and justice. This framework aligns with the humanitarian principles of impartiality and humanity, yet it adds a moral and practical imperative for inclusivity in post-conflict reconstruction.

However, as Ní Aoláin and Haynes caution, the impact of Resolution 1325 has been limited by its implementation gap.³⁶ Many states, Nigeria included, have adopted National Action Plans, yet funding, accountability, and enforcement remain non-existent or weak.³⁷ This reinforces the argument that while the governing principles of IHL is expanding to incorporate gender perspectives, its real-world application continues to fall short of transformative change.

3.3 The Nigerian Context: Women and Humanitarian Crises

Nigeria provides a very striking case study of how international humanitarian norms interact with complex internal realities. The country has endured recurrent armed conflicts and humanitarian emergencies, from the Biafran War (1967–1970) to the ongoing insurgencies in the North-East, communal clashes in the Middle Belt, and militarised responses to separatist movements in the

³⁴ Prosecutor v. Furundžija (Judgment) IT-95-17/1-T (10 December 1998) paras 171–173.

³⁵ UNSC Res 1325 (31 October 2000) UN Doc S/RES/1325.

³⁶ F Ní Aoláin and D Haynes, *UN Security Council Resolution 1325 and the Persistence of Inequality* (Oxford University Press 2018) 85–90.

³⁷ Federal Republic of Nigeria, *National Action Plan for the Implementation of UNSCR 1325 and Related Resolutions* (2017–2020).

South-East.³⁸ In each of these crises, women have borne a disproportionate share of the suffering, facing not only displacement and loss, but also gender-specific harms such as sexual violence, forced marriages, and deprivation of reproductive health services.³⁹

Under the structure of International Humanitarian Law, the Nigerian government is bound by the four Geneva Conventions and their Additional Protocols, which it ratified in 1961 and 1988 respectively.⁴⁰ Nigeria is also a State Party to key international and regional human rights instruments that emphasise gender protection in conflict, including the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) and the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol).⁴¹ Together, these instruments enforce obligations not only to refrain from gender-based violations but to actively prevent and punish them.

However, Nigeria's experience reveals that it is not the case in actual practice. Although the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) and the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs have collaborated on initiatives addressing gender and conflict, the institutional capacity continues to

³⁸ C Obi, *The Impact of Armed Conflict on Women and Children in Nigeria* (Centre for Conflict Research 2021) 12–14.

³⁹ Amnesty International, "They Betrayed Us": Women Who Survived Boko Haram Raped, Starved and Detained in Nigeria (Amnesty International Report 2018) 8–10.

⁴⁰ ICRC, *Treaties, States Parties and Commentaries: Nigeria* <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/states-parties/ng> accessed 15 October 2025.

⁴¹ Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (adopted 18 December 1979, entered into force 3 September 1981) 1249 UNTS 13 (CEDAW); Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (adopted 11 July 2003, entered into force 25 November 2005).

remain limited.⁴² Reports by the United Nations and local NGOs indicate that security forces and armed groups alike have been implicated in sexual violence and other violations against women, often with little or no accountability.⁴³ For instance, a 2020 Human Rights Watch report documented widespread sexual abuse of internally displaced women by security personnel in camps in Borno State.⁴⁴ These patterns reflect a deeper structural failure, one that is rooted in impunity, weak institutions, and cultural stigmas which surrounds gender and sexuality.

3.3.1 Gendered Harms and Displacement

The humanitarian fallout of Nigeria's prolonged conflicts continues to affect women and girls disproportionately. According to UNHCR estimates, women constitute over 54% of internally displaced persons (IDPs) in the North-East.⁴⁵ Many have lost access to livelihoods, healthcare, and education, and are exposed to sexual exploitation by both state and non-state actors.⁴⁶ Under IHL, the state bears the responsibility for ensuring humane treatment and protection of civilians, yet humanitarian access remains constrained by insecurity and governmental restrictions.⁴⁷

In addition, customary and religious norms intersect with gender to reinforce women's marginalisation. In displacement settings, widows and single women often lack property rights or

⁴² National Human Rights Commission (NHRC), Annual Report on Human Rights Protection in Conflict Zones (2022) 17–20.

⁴³ United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UNOCHA), Nigeria Humanitarian Response Plan 2023 (2023) 14–15.

⁴⁴ Human Rights Watch, “They Didn’t Know If I Was Alive or Dead”: Military Detention of Women and Children for Boko Haram-Related Offences in Northeast Nigeria (2020) 22–26.

⁴⁵ UNHCR, Nigeria IDP Statistics Report (2024) 5.

⁴⁶ *ibid* 45.

⁴⁷ International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), Nigeria: Humanitarian Situation Report (2023).

inheritance claims, which leaves them dependent on male relatives or humanitarian agencies.⁴⁸ This creates a cycle of vulnerability that humanitarian law alone cannot address unless it is accompanied by domestic legal reforms.

The Maputo Protocol, which Nigeria ratified in 2004, recognises women's rights to dignity, health, and protection during armed conflict (Article 11).⁴⁹ Despite this, Nigeria has yet to fully put into action these provisions within its domestic legal framework.

3.3.2 Legal and Institutional Barriers

Nigeria's dualist legal system complicates the incorporation of international humanitarian and human rights norms into domestic law. Under Section 12 of the 1999 Constitution (as amended), international treaties must be enacted by the National Assembly to have binding effect domestically.⁵⁰ Consequently, although Nigeria has ratified numerous conventions, their implementation often depends on ad hoc policies rather than enforceable statutes. This gap is particularly damaging for gender-related protections under IHL, which require proactive state measures.

Moreover, the Nigerian military justice system rarely prosecutes sexual and gender-based crimes committed during internal operations.⁵¹ The 2019 Presidential Panel on Human Rights Compliance by the Armed Forces acknowledged credible evidence of such violations, but only a few cases have led to convictions.⁵² Civilian victims, particularly women, also face significant

⁴⁸ M Okeke, 'Customary Law, Gender and Access to Property Rights in Displacement Contexts in Nigeria' (2020) 14(2) *African Journal of Gender and Law* 78, 84.

⁴⁹ Maputo Protocol (n 4) art 11.

⁵⁰ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) s 12.

⁵¹ S Ezeilo, 'Accountability for Sexual Violence in Conflict Situations: The Nigerian Experience' (2019) 5 *Nigerian Journal of Public Law* 112, 117.

⁵² Presidential Panel on Human Rights Compliance, *Final Report on the Review of Armed Forces Practices* (Abuja, 2019) 34–35.

barriers to reporting due to stigma, fear of reprisal, and limited access to legal aid.⁵³

Unfortunately, the situation of women in IDP camps illustrates the intersection of humanitarian and gender justice challenges. Nigerian courts have shown limited engagement with IHL principles, and there is very little jurisprudence applying Geneva or Maputo provisions to gender-based harms.⁵⁴ Without succinct judicial recognition and enforcement, international norms remain merely aspirational.

3.4 Towards a Gender-Responsive Humanitarian Law Framework

The evolution of gender discourse within International Humanitarian Law (IHL) continues to demonstrate a gradual, though incomplete, transition from a framework of protection to one of participation and agency. A genuinely gender-responsive humanitarian law framework must go beyond organizing protections for women to interrogating how systemic gender hierarchies shape access to justice, humanitarian assistance, and post-conflict recovery. This requires a dual transformation, that is normative and operational, where gender is not a supplementary concern but a structural principle embedded within every phase of humanitarian law interpretation and implementation.

At the normative level, gender responsiveness entails reinterpreting the existing corpus of IHL through a lens that is sensitive to the lived realities of women in conflict. This form of reinterpretation does not necessitate rewriting the Geneva Conventions, but rather adjusting their application to account for the intersectional dimensions of harm experienced by women and girls.⁵⁵ Intersectionality, acknowledging how gender interacts with class, ethnicity, displacement, and social marginalisation widens the protective capacity of IHL beyond narrow

⁵³ Women's Rights Advancement and Protection Alternative (WRAPA), *Barriers to Justice for Women in Conflict-Affected Areas of Nigeria* (2021) 16–19.

⁵⁴ E Nwogugu, 'International Humanitarian Law in Nigerian Courts: Prospects and Limitations' (2022) 3(1) *Nigerian Yearbook of International Law* 121.

⁵⁵ Hilary Charlesworth, Christine Chinkin and Shelley Wright, 'Feminist Approaches to International Law' (1991) 85 *American Journal of International Law* 613, 625.

definitions of sexual violence.⁵⁶ It also recognises that deprivation of economic security, forced displacement, and the breakdown of community structures are also gendered harms warranting redress under humanitarian principles.

Essentially, the move toward gender responsiveness calls for integrating women's participation in decision-making processes that govern humanitarian interventions and transitional justice mechanisms.⁵⁷ Women must not only be seen as recipients of aid or subjects of legal protection but as shapers of humanitarian priorities and implementers of accountability frameworks. This imperative fully aligns with the transformative vision of United Nations Security Council Resolution (UNSCR) 1325 and its subsequent resolutions, which underscore women's equal participation in all peace and security efforts.⁵⁸ It is rather disappointing that implementation remains inconsistent. Reports from conflict-affected regions reveal that gender considerations are often treated as peripheral "add-ons" rather than core obligations, leading to fragmented and symbolic inclusion.⁵⁹

In a bid to build a sustainable gender-responsive humanitarian law framework, attention must be directed toward strengthening national institutions and bodies responsible for the domestication and enforcement of IHL obligations as states bear the primary duty of translating international commitments into domestic practice. Yet, as Ní Aoláin argues, the gap between the rhetorical endorsement of women's rights and their material realisation in post-conflict societies remains vast.⁶⁰ This unfortunate disjunction is particularly visible in countries like Nigeria, where

⁵⁶ Kimberlé Crenshaw, 'Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence against Women of Color' (1991) 43 *Stanford Law Review* 1241, 1249–1252.

⁵⁷ Fionnuala Ní Aoláin, Naomi Cahn, Dina Haynes and Nahla Valji, *The Oxford Handbook of Gender and Conflict* (OUP 2018) 372–375.

⁵⁸ UNSC Res 1325 (31 October 2000) UN Doc S/RES/1325; UNSC Res 1820 (19 June 2008) UN Doc S/RES/1820.

⁵⁹ Sanam Naraghi Anderlini, *Women Building Peace: What They Do, Why It Matters* (Lynne Rienner Publishers 2007) 142–147.

⁶⁰ Fionnuala Ní Aoláin, 'Advancing Women's Rights in Conflict and Post-Conflict

patriarchal norms, resource constraints, and very weak judicial systems obstruct the enforcement of IHL's gender provisions. The challenge is not simply the absence of law but the absence of gender-conscious interpretation, intentional political will, and institutional accountability.

A holistic gender-responsive approach therefore demands collaboration between IHL, International Human Rights Law (IHRL), and the Women, Peace and Security (WPS) agenda. IHL's traditional focus on conduct during hostilities must interact with IHRL's broader concern for equality and dignity, ensuring that women's protection in conflict also extends into the post-conflict reconstruction phase.⁶¹ The integration of these regulations can enable a more reasonable normative framework, one that treats women's rights not as exceptional claims but as integral to the law's humanitarian purpose.

Feminist scholars emphasise that the transformation of IHL cannot be achieved solely through textual reforms or institutional adjustments; it requires a paradigmatic shift in how the international community views vulnerability and power.⁶² In my opinion, a gender-responsive humanitarian law framework should acknowledge women as political actors with agency, capable of contributing to the design of humanitarian responses and peacebuilding initiatives. Such a reimagining, that is grounded in both justice and equality, moves IHL closer to fulfilling its core humanitarian standards, protecting human dignity in all its diverse expressions.

4. Operational and Legal Realities in Nigeria's Humanitarian Context

Situations' (2016) 22 *International Journal of Human Rights* 803, 812–813.

⁶¹ Louise Doswald-Beck, 'Human Rights and International Humanitarian Law: Their Relationship and Interaction in Practice' (2011) 90 *International Review of the Red Cross* 883, 887–889.

⁶² Dianne Otto, 'Beyond Legal Reforms: Gender and the Politics of Inclusion in International Law' (2016) 17 *Melbourne Journal of International Law* 1, 10–12.

4.1 Operational Challenges in Conflict Zones

The North-East insurgency, driven by Boko Haram and other non-state armed groups, also regarded as terrorists, has generated one of the largest humanitarian crises in Nigeria. As of 2024, UNHCR estimates over 2 million internally displaced persons, with women comprising more than 54% of this population.⁶³ Women face a spectrum of gendered harms, including sexual violence, forced marriage, abductions, deprivation of reproductive health services, and restricted access to education and livelihoods.⁶⁴ On the 17th of November 2025 more than two dozen girls from an all girls boarding school in Kebbi State were viciously abducted by armed men deemed terrorists, this is the second all girls attack since the 2014 Chibok Girls abductions.

The implementation of IHL principles in these contexts is further complicated by security constraints and governmental inefficiencies. Humanitarian access is often limited due to active hostilities or military restrictions, which undermines the delivery of essential services.⁶⁵ IDP camps, though seemingly safe spaces, frequently expose women to exploitation and abuse, including sexual harassment and coercion by both state actors and camp administrators.⁶⁶

Unfortunately, judicial remedies for these abuses remain scarce. Cases of sexual and gender-based violence committed during counterinsurgency operations are rarely prosecuted, and civil society organisations report widespread immunity for perpetrators.⁶⁷ Military courts, where many allegations arise, often lack gender-sensitive procedures, while civilian courts are overburdened and geographically inaccessible to displaced populations.⁶⁸

⁶³ UNHCR, Nigeria IDP Statistics Report (2024) 5.

⁶⁴ Amnesty International, “They Betrayed Us”: Women Who Survived Boko Haram Raped, Starved and Detained in Nigeria (2018) 8–10.

⁶⁵ UNOCHA, Nigeria Humanitarian Response Plan 2023 (2023) 14–15.

⁶⁶ Human Rights Watch, “They Didn’t Know If I Was Alive or Dead”: Military Detention of Women and Children for Boko Haram-Related Offences in Northeast Nigeria (2020) 22–26.

⁶⁷ *ibid.*

⁶⁸ S Ezeilo, ‘Accountability for Sexual Violence in Conflict Situations: The Nigerian Experience’ (2019) 5 Nigerian Journal of Public Law 112, 117.

4.2 Barriers to Accessing Justice

Despite the presence of legal instruments and international obligations, women in these conflict-affected areas of Nigeria face intimidating barriers to justice. The cultural norms and patriarchal social structures in Nigeria frequently discourage survivors from reporting abuses, particularly sexual violence, for fear of stigma, ostracism, or even retribution.⁶⁹ Legal literacy is extremely limited among women in IDP camps, which further constraints their ability to navigate judicial processes or claim remedies.⁷⁰

The systematic deficiencies continue to compound these societal barriers. Law enforcement agencies often lack training in handling gender-based crimes and may exhibit bias against female victims.⁷¹ The courts are frequently overburdened, and procedural delays continue to prolong cases for years, thereby discouraging the pursuit of justice.⁷² In many northern states, customary and Sharia courts exercise concurrent jurisdiction, but their treatment of women's rights under IHL and human rights instruments is inconsistent and often times inadequate.⁷³

4.3 Gaps in Humanitarian Law Implementation

The total Implementation of IHL principles in Nigeria faces multiple challenges. The coordination between federal and state humanitarian authorities is frequently weak, which results in

⁶⁹ Amnesty International, "They Betrayed Us": Women Who Survived Boko Haram Raped, Starved and Detained in Nigeria (2018) 14.

⁷⁰ Women's Rights Advancement and Protection Alternative (WRAPA), *Barriers to Justice for Women in Conflict-Affected Areas of Nigeria* (2021) 21–23.

⁷¹ *ibid* 25.

⁷² S Ezeilo, 'Accountability for Sexual Violence in Conflict Situations: The Nigerian Experience' (2019) 5 *Nigerian Journal of Public Law* 112, 118–119.

⁷³ Fatima Lemu, *Customary and Sharia Law in Northern Nigeria: Implications for Women's Rights* (University of Jos Press 2020) 87–92.

fragmented service delivery.⁷⁴ Also, security concerns in insurgency-affected regions limit the ability of both governmental and non-governmental actors to reach women in need.⁷⁵ Humanitarian aid distribution is often conducted without gender-sensitive oversight, which leaves women disproportionately disadvantaged.⁷⁶

Additionally, the prosecution of gender-based violations under the VAPP Act hardly aligns with international standards. Most times cases of sexual violence, forced marriage, and abductions often go uninvestigated or are prosecuted under inappropriate legal frameworks, thereby undermining the protections guaranteed under both IHL and the VAPP Act.⁷⁷ The lack of female legal practitioners ready to advocate and law enforcement officers in conflict zones further diminishes survivors' access to justice and protection.⁷⁸

4.5 Policy and Institutional Recommendations

A gender-responsive humanitarian law framework in Nigeria must address both legal and operational deficits. In the first place, domestic legislation should completely correlate with international obligations, ensuring the consistent application of the VAPP Act and integration of IHL principles at state levels.⁷⁹ All states should also be encouraged to domesticate all ratified treaties and develop monitoring mechanisms for their enforcement.

Secondly, institutional capacity-building is very essential. Law enforcement agencies, military personnel, and humanitarian actors require gender-sensitive training to identify, prevent, and

⁷⁴ UNOCHA, Nigeria Humanitarian Response Plan 2023 (2023) 18–19.

⁷⁵ *ibid* 14–15.

⁷⁶ Human Rights Watch, “They Didn’t Know If I Was Alive or Dead” (2020) 24– 27.

⁷⁷ CLEEN Foundation, State-Level Implementation of the VAPP Act in Nigeria: Progress and Challenges (2022) 12–15.

⁷⁸ *ibid* 16.

⁷⁹ *ibid*; Federal Republic of Nigeria, National Action Plan on UNSCR 1325 (2021).

respond to violations.⁸⁰ Specialized gender desks within police and judicial institutions can provide accessible, trauma-informed services to women survivors.⁸¹

Furthermore, women's meaningful participation in decision-making processes must be ensured. This includes integrating women into humanitarian coordination committees, peacebuilding initiatives, and policy advisory boards.⁸² Their perspectives can inform more effective programming and accountability mechanisms, thereby bridging the gap between international legal frameworks and lived realities on the ground, ensuring that they are not just viewed as people to be merely protected but as agents of justice, peacebuilding and legal reform.

Finally, civil society and international organisations play a very critical role in supporting implementation. Advocacy, monitoring, and reporting initiatives can hold the government accountable and ensure that both domestic and international norms are respected.⁸³ Carrying out complementary public education campaigns can also challenge patriarchal norms that hinder women's access to justice and protection, fostering a culture that respects women's rights as central to humanitarian law.

5. Conclusion

This article has examined the intersection of gender, humanitarian law, and Nigeria's humanitarian crises, highlighting both the standard promise of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and the operational realities on the ground. This analysis has demonstrated that while international treaties, conventions, and resolutions provide a robust framework for protecting women during armed conflicts, the translation of these norms into Nigerian domestic law and

⁸⁰ Fionnuala Ní Aoláin, Naomi Cahn, Dina Haynes and Nahla Valji, *The Oxford Handbook of Gender and Conflict* (OUP 2018) 374–375.

⁸¹ WRAPA, *Barriers to Justice for Women in Conflict-Affected Areas of Nigeria* (2021) 29.

⁸² UNSC Res 1325 (31 October 2000) UN Doc S/RES/1325; UNSC Res 1820 (19 June 2008) UN Doc S/RES/1820.

⁸³ Naraghi Anderlini, *Women Building Peace* (n 9) 150–152.

practice continues to remain incomplete and inconsistent.⁸⁴

The Nigerian context illustrates the complexity of implementing IHL and gender protections simultaneously, despite the ratification of key instruments, including the Geneva Conventions, CEDAW, and the Maputo Protocol, and the enactment of domestic legislation such as the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015, structural, institutional, and sociocultural barriers continue to hinder meaningful protection for women.⁸⁵ The North-East insurgency and other abductions and crises in the country has further exposed gaps in operational capacity, access to justice, and the practical application of gender-sensitive humanitarian interventions.⁸⁶

A gender-responsive humanitarian law framework in Nigeria requires more than legal reform; it necessitates the integration of gender principles across all levels of policy, institutional practice, and humanitarian operations.⁸⁷ Which will then strengthen the capacity of law enforcement, judicial, and humanitarian agencies, and ensure women's meaningful participation in decision-making, merging domestic laws with international obligations which are central to

⁸⁴ Hilary Charlesworth, Christine Chinkin and Shelley Wright, 'Feminist Approaches to International Law' (1991) 85 *American Journal of International Law* 613, 625.

⁸⁵ Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015; Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (adopted 18 December 1979, entered into force 3 September 1981) 1249 UNTS 13; Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (adopted 11 July 2003, entered into force 25 November 2005).

⁸⁶ UNHCR, Nigeria IDP Statistics Report (2024) 5; Human Rights Watch, "They Didn't Know If I Was Alive or Dead" (2020) 22–26.

⁸⁷ Fionnuala Ní Aoláin, Naomi Cahn, Dina Haynes and Nahla Valji, *The Oxford Handbook of Gender and Conflict* (OUP 2018) 374–375.

advancing this agenda.⁸⁸ Moreover, civil society and international actors play a pivotal role in monitoring, advocating, and providing gender-sensitive support in conflict-affected areas.⁸⁹

Ultimately, bridging the gap between normative ideals and lived realities requires a shift in both legal interpretation and operational priorities. We have to begin to recognise or rather see women not merely as beneficiaries of protection but as agents of change and contributors to peacebuilding as this is essential for achieving the transformative promise of IHL.⁹⁰ By embedding gender as a structural principle within humanitarian law, Nigeria can move closer to fulfilling its obligations under international law and ensuring the protection, dignity, and agency of women in times of conflict.

The Nigerian experience thus emphasises a broader lesson for global humanitarian law, that is, legal frameworks, however robust, achieve their humanitarian purpose only when gender-conscious interpretation, institutional accountability, and operational inclusion converge. Future learning and practice should continue to interrogate these dynamics, seeking innovative strategies to ensure that women's rights are central, rather than peripheral, to humanitarian law.

Author's Note

Sandra S. John is a Nigerian-trained lawyer with a keen interest in international humanitarian law, human rights, and gender justice. Her research explores the intersection of legal frameworks, gendered vulnerability, and the operational realities of humanitarian crises in Nigeria and beyond.

⁸⁸ Federal Republic of Nigeria, National Action Plan on UNSCR 1325 (2021); CLEEN Foundation, *State-Level Implementation of the VAPP Act in Nigeria: Progress and Challenges* (2022) 12–15.

⁸⁹ Sanam Naraghi Anderlini, *Women Building Peace: What They Do, Why It Matters* (Lynne Rienner Publishers 2007) 150–152.

⁹⁰ Dianne Otto, 'Beyond Legal Reforms: Gender and the Politics of Inclusion in International Law' (2016) 17 *Melbourne Journal of International Law* 1, 10–12.

This article reflects her commitment to advancing gender-sensitive approaches within humanitarian law and promoting the effective protection and agency of women in conflict-affected contexts. It draws on both international legal norms and domestic Nigerian experiences to provide a nuanced perspective on bridging the gap between theory and practice in the field of humanitarian law.